

ISSN: 2507-7589 ◦ EISSN: 2507-7619

Recueil De Mécanique
El Wancharissi University
of Tissemsilt

Research Paper

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.7216713

Open access

Optimal PID controllers design for discharge pressure-temperature control of centrifugal gas compressor system using Grey Wolf optimizer

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history :

Received 15 September 22

Accepted 17 October 22

Keywords:

PID Controller, Grey Wolf Optimizer,
Centrifugal Gas Compressor System, Gas
Turbine, Control System.

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce optimal PID controllers that are designed with the help of the recently developed metaheuristic Stochastic Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO), with the gains K_p , K_i , and K_d of the controllers chosen via the minimization of the integral quadratic tracking error function $e(t)$. This is done so that we can achieve the best control specifications, including no overshooting, good response and settling time, and no static error. The primary goal of this design is to improve the best performance and efficiency of the BCL 505 centrifugal gas compressor system, which is installed in the Hassi R'mel Gas Field in the south of Algeria. A GE 5002C Gas Turbine entrains this system with two shafts, where the goal is for the two outputs discharge pressure and temperature P_2 and T_2 , respectively, to coincide to its desired references, based on two PID controllers.

1 Introduction

Many different types of industrial procedures can be modelled using time-invariant linear systems. Because of this, throughout the course of the last few decades, a great number of technologically advanced control methods have been developed for such systems. Probably the most well-known controls are the Gaussian Quadratic Linear Control, the H Control, and the Pole Placement Control. These methods have been used successfully, but there are two big problems with them that keep them from being widely used in industry. In practice, the design of the studied system's control must be accurately created in this regard. On the one hand, if it is very complex, it cannot be used for design. On the other hand, if it is overly basic, it does not adequately depict the behaviour of the system. As a result of these difficulties, the PID kind of control has become prevalent in the business, thus it is frequently necessary to apply this sort of command. A further benefit of utilizing PID controllers is the availability of simple approaches that take minimal time and effort from the engineer when determining the gains of these regulators. These methods include the commonly used Ziegler-Nichols (ZN) and Cohen and Coon (CC) methods [1-3]. Indeed, this strategy involves a pretty straightforward experimental test. Gains of the regulator are

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calculated using charts or basic formulas based on two or three test-related data. Nevertheless, this strategy can optimize the deviation between actual and desired outputs. Other economic quantities, such as the control effort, cannot be decreased. New tuning techniques that take into account many objectives may be a dependable way to bypass this disadvantage. In this context, our objectives for constructing PID-type regulators through GWO [4] are as follows: These algorithms enable the automatic tweaking of regulators.

2 Centrifugal gas compressor (BCL 505 system)

Centrifugal compressors are used in many industries, such as the oil industry, the production of thermal and nuclear energy, the propulsion of aircraft, the distribution of water, and so on. In fact, you need to know how these devices work in order to improve their performance and lower their operating costs. In this case, one of the limits of how these systems can be used is set by their stability limits. Beyond these limits, the systems can no longer be sure to work in a stable way. This paper looks at the BCL 505 type of gas compressor, which is a type of centrifugal gas compressor. Table.1 shows what it looks like and what it does.

Table 1 - General performance of centrifugal gas compressor BCL 505

Parameters	Values
Stages	1-5
Maximum discharge pressure	123 kg/cm ²
Maximum discharge temperature	121 °C
Efficiently	73 %
Speed	3000 to 20000 rpm
Compressed Gas	LNG

Fig. 1 – Centrifugal gas compressor BCL 505 body, with real view in vertical joint plane

The Nuovo Pignone company is responsible for the construction of this compressor, which is put to use in heavy-duty gas compression applications such as the development of gas fields and the transit of gas networks. It is outfitted with a computer-based control room that includes the DCS as a component. This configuration enables inputs/outputs measurements to be taken directly from the sensors that have been placed. The centrifugal gas compressor that was researched for this paper's principal purpose was to ensure the pressure rise of the continuous flow of gas that was passing through it while it was based on kinetic energy. Where Compressors are utilized for a variety of purposes, including but not limited to the following:

- Reach a level of gas pressure.
- The compressors are divided into groups based on how they work and the type of gas they are meant to compress.
- Air and gas compressors, depending on the movement of the moving parts, such as linear or rotary motion, or the operating principle, such as volumetric compressors and dynamic compressors which are the application area of the present paper [5].

3 The Grey Wolf Optimizer principle

A new robust meta-heuristic optimization algorithm called the Grey Wolf Optimizer had been introduced by S. Mirjalili et al. [4] and [5]. It has been developed mainly to solve the non-convex engineering optimization problem. It possesses some main features compared to its analytical count parts methods, such as it is inspired by nature behaviors concept, which can typically be related to several natural physical phenomena, it has a straightforward idea that allows for easy implementation. GWO is very flexible and can be applied to many different problems without any particular changes in the structure of the algorithm from its initial version, and the critical issue is that it does not require any matrix or derivatives calculation, making it very competitive for complex problems and highly suitable for real problems with expensive or unknown derivative information [4] and [5]. This algorithm is inspired by the natural behavior of the Grey Wolf, which belongs to a specified and elected family called the “Canidae family.” Indeed, the Grey Wolves are classified as high predators, meaning they are at the top of the food provision sequence. They prefer to live in groups of 5 to 12 maximum under a pyramidal social dominant policy, as shown in Fig 2. The dominant wolves, named alpha (α) wolves, consist of males and females responsible for making decisions, hunting, and other activities. They dictate orders and findings to others, but sometimes some democracy takes place where alpha wolves listen to others in the group. Although the alpha wolves are not necessarily the most vital, they are followed by other wolves named leading wolves [4] and [5].

Fig. 2 – The Pyramidal

levels principle of the grey

wolves

The second group is known as beta wolves (β). Beta wolves, which can be either male or female, provide support and supervision to alpha wolves and are considered the top choice to take over when an alpha wolf dies or disappears. They're submissive to alpha wolves yet have some authority over lower-ranking wolves. Delta (Δ) wolves are the lowest rating level and are frequently used as scapegoats. They are merely obeying orders by taking on the dominant pack. But if even one delta wolf were to be absent, deadly hostilities would break out. Wolf packs with an omega (ω) pack are subservient to the pack with a higher pack rank. However, they are still responsible for leading the pack's lower-ranking kappa (κ) and lambda (λ) wolves, which include the pack's elders, scouts, hunters, caretakers, and sentinels. Individuals designated as sentinels keep the rest of the community safe. Wolves with a lot of life experience can become alpha or beta if they're not already. The group's alphas and betas rely on their hunter allies to help them find food and quarry. The sick, injured, and weak wolves in the pack are now the responsibility of the caregivers. Hunting grey wolves consists primarily of the following activities, as described by Muro et al. [4] and [5]:

- The process of locating, pursuing, and closing in on the prey.
- The phase consisting of pursuing and encircling the target.
- The predator will harass the victim until it stops moving, at which point it will launch an attack.

The GWO algorithm imitates and models the natural hunting behavior of grey wolves, including their use of pyramid clusters. This algorithm operates on the presumption that the optimal or most suitable answer is denoted by the letter alpha (α). As a consequence of this, the solutions beta (β) and delta (Δ) are, respectively, the second and third best options. The remaining

potential answers are denoted by the Greek letters omega (ω), kappa (k), and lambda (λ), respectively. The and wolves direct the optimization process that occurs within the GWO algorithm. This process corresponds to the hunting process that is used to capture the intended prey. These three wolves are being followed by the pack. In order to create a mathematical representation of the encircling behavior, the authors [4] and [5] proposed the following equations:

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_{prey}(t) - \vec{X}_{Gwolf}(t)| \tag{1}$$

$$\vec{X}_{Gwolf}(t + 1) = \vec{X}_{prey}(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \tag{2}$$

Where t indicates the current iteration, \vec{A} and \vec{C} are coefficient vectors, \vec{X}_{prey} is the position vector of the prey, and \vec{X}_{Gwolf} indicates the position vector of a grey wolf. The vectors \vec{A} and \vec{C} are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \vec{A} = 2\vec{a} \cdot \vec{r}_1 - \vec{a} \\ \vec{C} = 2 \cdot \vec{r}_2 \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Where the entries of \vec{a} are linearly decreased from 2 to 0 over the number of iterations, and \vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_2 are random vectors whose entries are varying within the interval of $[0, 1]$. To clarify the effect of equations (1) and (2) a 2D position vector and the possible positions of the neighbours.

The random and actual positions vectors show that the grey wolves have the potential to reach any position among the various available sites. This is explained in reference [20]. Consequently, a grey wolf is able to update its status inside the space around the prey in any arbitrary place by utilizing equations (1) and (2), as depicted in figure 4. Gray wolves are capable of locating the exact location of their prey and then maneuvering themselves into a circle around it. While the beta and delta wolves assist in the hunting process, the alpha wolf is the one who is in charge of it. However, within a limited search space that has been designated, the precise position of the perfect prey cannot initially be determined. As a result, it is presumable that the alpha wolf will present the best candidate solution while the mathematical model is being run through its paces in order to replicate the hunting process that grey wolves engage in. The beta and delta wolves are in possession of more accurate knowledge regarding the possible location of the prey. In this circumstance, the three first best solutions obtained up until the actual iteration are memorized, and all of the other search candidates, including the delta, the kappa, and the lambda, are compelled to update their positions in accordance with the location of the best search candidate obtained up until this point. Based on equations (4), (5), and (6), respectively, the positions of the initial three search candidates, alpha, beta, and delta, can be updated.

Fig. 3 – The principle of the position updating

$$\vec{D}_\alpha = |\vec{C}_1 \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}| \tag{4}$$

$$\vec{D}_\beta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}| \tag{5}$$

$$\vec{D}_\Delta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\Delta - \vec{X}| \tag{6}$$

The position vector of the prey with respect to alpha, beta and delta wolves can be calculated using the following mathematical formulation:

$$\vec{X}_1 = \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha) \tag{7}$$

$$\vec{X}_2 = \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta) \tag{8}$$

$$\vec{X}_3 = \vec{X}_\Delta - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\Delta) \tag{9}$$

The best position can be calculated by taking and average of alpha, beta and delta wolves' positions as follows:

$$\vec{X}(t + 1) = \frac{1}{3}(\vec{X}_1 + \vec{X}_2 + \vec{X}_3) \tag{10}$$

The objective function that should be minimized to obtain the optimal PID parameters is:

$$J = \int e(t)^2 dt \tag{11}$$

4 Proposed Method Steps

The pseudo codes the GWO algorithm are given by following steps:

Step 1: Define the input data including the system base configuration, branch impedance and bus data (load real and reactive power).

Step 2: Initialize GWO parameters (maximum number iterations *iter*, population size, *PS*, and vectors variables: \vec{a} , \vec{A} and \vec{C})

Step 3: Initialize the positions of PMUs randomly in the power system.

Step 4: Evaluate the fitness function value $F_{obj}(X)$.

Step 5: Update leader wolves X_α , X_β and X_δ (the first three best search agents).

Step 6: calculate the coefficient vectors (\vec{A} , \vec{C} and \vec{a}).

Step 7: Update the wolf's position.

Step 8: Repeat procedure from step 4 to step 7 up to the maximum predefined number of iterations. The last X_α presents the solution of problem [4] and [5].

5 Application and Results

The system under study is a gas Turbo-compressor which is installed in Hassi R'mel Natural gas pumping station. It comprises two inputs, T1 and P1 (aspiration temperature and pressure), and two outputs, T2 and P2 (discharge temperature and pressure). Fig. 4 shows the schematic block diagram of the inputs/outputs signals and the turbine which drives the studied compressor.

Fig. 4 – Schematic block diagram of Turbo-compressor system

The selected model of the studied gas turbo-compressor system from the comparison study is a linear model which is presented in state space block observable canonical form, and it is given as follows:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0152 & 0.0185 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0389 & 0.0436 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0666 & 0.0696 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0881 & 0.1080 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0959 & 0.0784 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0508 & 0.0701 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.0171 & 0.0319 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.1294 & 0.0158 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -0.0052 & 0.0145 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0.0699 & 0.0038 \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} 0.0245 & 0.0262 \\ 0.0686 & 0.0045 \\ 0.0219 & 0.0425 \\ 0.0199 & 0.0710 \\ 0.0820 & 0.2317 \\ 0.1615 & 0.1233 \\ 0.1762 & 0.0941 \\ 0.3274 & 0.1871 \\ 0.0857 & 0.2576 \\ -0.0801 & -0.0413 \end{pmatrix}, \quad C^T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad D = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

After the tuning of the two controllers using the GWO optimization algorithm as shown in Fig 5 et Fig 6 respectively, the parameters gain of the two controllers are given as follows: PID pressure controller, $PID_P = (K_p= 182.14, K_i= 224.71, K_d= 76.66)$ and $PID_T = (K_p= 33.67, K_i= 152.51, K_d= 42.21)$.

Based on the obtained results, we see that the actual outputs of the discharge pressure and temperature Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 coincide with their references with minimal errors, no overshooting, and peaks, and the proposed controller achieved the desired specifications.

Fig. 5 – The evolution of the grey wolf population

Fig. 6 – The change of J in terms of GWO iteration

Fig. 7 – Output signal of reference and real discharge pressure

Fig. 8 – Output signal of reference and real discharge temperature

6 Conclusion

This work aims to develop two optimal PID controllers, i.e., select the optimal parameters K_d , K_p , and K_i , based on the proposed GWO algorithm, which permits minimizing the square integral error criteria. The obtained results prove their computing time, simplicity in implementation, and maintaining the stability and efficiency of the operating thermodynamics parameters inputs/outputs: pressure and temperature of the studied centrifugal gas compressor.

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